

Linear Rayleigh-Taylor instability of rotating viscous fluids .

A. de Andrea González,* J. M. Gandarias Villanueva,[†] and L.M. González-Gutiérrez[†]

(Dated: June 22, 2023)

Abstract

The Rayleigh-Taylor instability is studied for the viscous and non-viscous case of two fluids of finite thickness, subjected to rotation around an axis perpendicular to the direction of acceleration. The effect of surface tension is also taken into account. For the non-viscous case, the combined effect of finite thickness and rotation modify the cut-off wave number due to surface tension. However, for the viscous case, the cut-off wave number remains unchanged. Likewise, it is verified that the wavelength of the mode of maximum instability reaches a limit value due to the action of surface tension.

* Departamento de Física, Escuela Politécnica Superior, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Av. Universidad 30, 28911 Leganés, Spain

[†] School of Naval Engineering, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), Avda. de la Memoria 4 28040 Madrid Spain

I. INTRODUCTION

Normally the Rayleigh-Taylor instability (RTI) appears when a heavy fluid overlies a lighter fluid [1], [2] and gravity is oriented towards the light fluid, in other words, the density gradient and gravity are opposed. This situation is present in a wide variety of applications: ferrofluids [3], tectonics [4], exploding foils [5], aerobreakup [6], and astrophysics [7], [8]. An original extension of the RTI appears in the sloshing phenomena when two different fluids are confined in a accelerated tank. In this case, the light fluid overlies a heavier fluid when gravity is present, but the RTI appears when a larger acceleration than gravity is applied to both fluids in the opposite direction to the force of gravity. As explained before, the density gradient is opposed to the difference between the inertial force and gravity.

Mikaelian [9] analyzed the Rayleigh-Taylor instability in two finite-thickness fluids taking viscosity effects into account. A numerical dispersion relation was obtained for different thicknesses and Atwood numbers. He performed a stability analysis in a one-dimensional geometry (1D) based on two fluids separated with a sharp interface using homogeneous Dirichlet and Neumann conditions for the velocity at the top and bottom boundaries, and compatibility conditions at the interface.

The complete linear RTI problem, considering the effects of viscosity, finite thickness and surface tension, was solved numerically by J. Martínez-Carrascal *et al.* [10]. For this purpose, these authors used regularized densities and viscosities according to a function of the hyperbolic tangent type. They obtained the instability growth rate in both 1D and 2D (two-dimensional) geometry, achieving good agreement. Furthermore, for the 2D geometry they represented some eigenfunctions of interest. The 2D extension presented in this work allows the analysis of more complex flows and includes the possibility of studying diffuse interfaces being the sharp interface being just a particular case.

It is well-established that the Coriolis force that acts on fluid in a rotating system can act to stabilise otherwise unstable flows.

The effect of rotation on the Rayleigh-Taylor instability was studied by Hide [11], [12] by using a variational principle to obtain explicit, though approximate solutions. For a fluid of exponentially varying density bounded by two horizontal rigid plates, Hide found that rotation tends to inhibit RTI through viscous effects [12], taking the axis of rotation along the vertical direction. On the other hand, for two uniform semi-infinite fluids separated by

horizontal surface, he discussed the effect of rotation in the cases of low and high rotation. In both cases, he showed that the effect of rotation is to increase the wavelength of the mode of maximum instability and to decrease its growth rate, i.e. rotation slows the growth of the instability.

The aforementioned RTI analysis for two semi-infinite fluids previously analyzed by Hide [12] was further simplified by Chandrasekhar [13] neglecting the effect of viscosity. This author concluded that an unstable configuration could not be stabilised indefinitely by rotation. Likewise, when surface tension is taken into account, the cut-off wave number is not affected by rotation. This fact was also later verified by Sharma *et al.* [14].

Baldwin *et al.*[15] show experimentally that rotation about an axis normal to the interface acts to retard the growth rate of the instability and stabilise long wavelength modes. The results agree qualitatively with Hide's. Moreover, these authors suggest that rotation acts to stabilise long wavelength instabilities, while viscosity stabilises short wavelength instabilities.

Tao *et al.* [16] obtained an analytical expression of the RTI linear growth rate in a rotating system with the axis of rotation normal to the acceleration of the interface between two uniform inviscid fluids. They found that the Coriolis force always diminished the aforementioned growth rate and that this retardation effect becomes stronger when the Atwood number is increased. These authors also speculated on the use of rotation to suppress RTI in the spherical pellets used in inertial confinement fusion.

However, to the best of our knowledge no study of rotating RTI including viscosity, surface tension and finite thickness effect has been performed. Therefore, we shall extend the analysis of Tao [16] including viscosity, surface tension and finite thickness effect.

In this paper we perform this survey in the case of one-dimensional (1D) and two-dimensional (2D) geometries.

Similarly to [17], a hyperbolic tangent distribution for the density and viscosity profiles are imposed, which allows skipping the compatibility conditions when sharp interfaces are simulated.

The paper is organised as follows: in section II the general description to the RTI is explained and the general equations are presented. In section III the 1D formulation is detailed. In section IV, the results obtained by both methodologies for the VRTI problem are compared. Finally, conclusions are presented in section V.

II. PROBLEM SETUP

The strategies to perform the linear stability analysis are presented in this section. To study the viscous version of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability (VRTI), we assume a zero velocity base-flow and regularized density and viscosity distributions that represent two fluids separated by a common interface. We analyze the evolution of the perturbations by the assumed base-flow. The calculations have been performed in a 1D computational domain.

Let ρ_1, μ_1, ν_1 and ρ_2, μ_2, ν_2 be the densities, and the kinematic and dynamic viscosities of the top-(heavy) and bottom-(light) fluids respectively. The two phase flow is governed by the incompressible Newtonian Navier-Stokes equations in a domain Ω in the presence of gravity g , which imply mass and momentum conservation, and a density transport equation. As the velocity baseflow is zero, the viscosity transport equation is not necessary in this VRTI formulation, see [18]. The domain is mathematically expressed as $\Omega = [-H, H]$.

Similarly to [19], the characteristic time, length, velocity, pressure, density and viscosity scales used to transform the problem to its non-dimensional version are defined as:

$$\rho_o = \frac{\rho_1 + \rho_2}{2} \quad \mu_o = \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2} \quad \nu_o = \frac{\nu_1 + \nu_2}{2}, \quad (1)$$

$$t_o = (\nu_o/g^2)^{1/3} \quad l_o = (\nu_o^2/g)^{1/3} \quad u_o = (g\nu_o)^{1/3}, \quad (2)$$

$$k_o = (\nu_o^2/g)^{-1/3} \quad p_o = \rho_o g (\nu_o^2/g)^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

The non-dimensional version of this set of equations reads:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \rho \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} = -\nabla p + \rho \mathbf{u}_g + \nabla[\mu(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)] + 2\rho(\mathbf{u} \times \boldsymbol{\Omega}), \quad (4)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \rho = 0. \quad (6)$$

where $\rho, \mathbf{u}, p, t, \nabla, \mu, \tau, \mathbf{u}_g$ are the non-dimensional density, velocity, pressure, time, nabla operator, viscosity, viscous stress tensor and unity vector representing gravity.

A steady nonparallel basic flow $(\bar{u}_i, \bar{\rho}, \bar{p})$ is perturbed by small-amplitude velocity \tilde{u}_i , density $\tilde{\rho}$ and pressure \tilde{p} perturbations, as follows:

$$u_i(x, y, z, t) = \bar{u}(y) + \varepsilon \tilde{u}(x, y, z, t) + c.c. \quad (7)$$

$$p(x, y, z, t) = \bar{p}(y) + \varepsilon \tilde{p}(x, y, z, t) + c.c. \quad (8)$$

$$\rho(x, y, z, t) = \bar{\rho}(y) + \varepsilon \tilde{\rho}(x, y, z, t) + c.c. \quad (9)$$

where $\varepsilon \ll 1$, and *c.c.* denotes the conjugate of the complex quantities \tilde{u}_i , $\tilde{\rho}$ and \tilde{p} . As baseflow, we consider two superposed fluids at rest $\bar{u}_i = 0$ separated by a regularized interface at $y = 0$ and subjected to a constant gravitational acceleration pointing downwards the vertical direction y .

Therefore, in order to describe the Rayleigh-Taylor (RT) instability of sharp interface, it seems more consistent to attempt to solve the problem for a transition layer of finite thickness, and then take the limit when the thickness tends to zero. Similarly to the sharp jump implementation used in [17], we adopt the density and viscosity profiles

$$\bar{\rho} = 1 + A_\rho \tanh(y/L_s) \quad \mu = 1 + A_\mu \tanh(y/L_s) \quad (10)$$

where L_s is the gradient scale length of the density and viscosity layers and A_ρ, A_μ the Atwood numbers given by

$$A_\rho = \frac{\rho_1 - \rho_2}{\rho_1 + \rho_2} \quad A_\mu = \frac{\mu_1 - \mu_2}{\mu_1 + \mu_2} \quad (11)$$

Taking account of equations (10), typical air-water hydrodynamic instabilities in the presence of a sharp interface can be recovered by setting $L_s \rightarrow 0$. When equations (7), (8) and (9) are substituted into the Navier-Stokes equations (4), (5) and 6, assuming zero base flow $\bar{u}_i = 0$ and neglecting second order terms, the linearized Navier-Stokes equations for the perturbation quantities are obtained:

$$\bar{\rho} \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_i}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x_i} + \mu \Delta \hat{u}_i + \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{u}_j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_i}{\partial x_j} \right) \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial x_j} + 2\bar{\rho} \epsilon_{ijk} \tilde{u}_i \Omega_k + \tilde{\rho} u_{g_i} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\rho}}{\partial t} + \tilde{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{\rho}}{\partial x_j} = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{u}_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (14)$$

Since the coefficients of \tilde{u}_i , $\tilde{\rho}$ and \tilde{p} do not depend on z and t the perturbation quantities can be written as normal modes

$$\tilde{u}_i(x, y, z, t) = \hat{u}_i(x) e^{ik_x x} e^{ik_z z} e^{\gamma t} + \text{c.c.}, \quad (15a)$$

$$\tilde{p}(x, y, z, t) = \hat{p}(x) e^{ik_x x} e^{ik_z z} e^{\gamma t} + \text{c.c.}, \quad (15b)$$

$$\tilde{\rho}(x, y, z, t) = \hat{\rho}(x) e^{ik_x x} e^{ik_z z} e^{\gamma t} + \text{c.c.}, \quad (15c)$$

which assumes periodic solution in both the horizontal x and spanwise z directions. Moreover, the complex conjugate (c.c.) is required to render the perturbations real. Additionally, $\gamma = \sigma + i\omega \in \mathbb{C}$ is the complex growth/decay rate σ and oscillation frequency ω .

Let us add the presence of the surface tension on the free surface that separates both fluid phases to this perturbed system. Following [19], the surface tension presence adds the term $-2(\partial_{xx}\hat{\xi}_s - k_z^2\hat{\xi}_s)S\delta_s(y - y_s)$ to the y projection of the equation (12). Where $\hat{\xi}_s = \hat{\xi}(x, y_s) e^{k_z z} e^{\gamma t}$ is the vertical displacement of the free surface at $y = y_s$, $\delta_s(y - y_s)$ is the Dirac's delta function and S is the non-dimensional surface tension, which can be expressed as:

$$S = \frac{T_s}{(\rho_1 + \rho_2)(g\nu^4)^{1/3}} \quad (16)$$

where T_s is the dimensional surface tension. In order to proceed with the numerical integration, the Dirac delta function will be regularized and the term $\hat{\xi}$ can be related to the vertical velocity perturbation \hat{v} as

$$\hat{v} = \frac{\partial \hat{\xi}}{\partial t} = \gamma \hat{\xi} \quad (17)$$

III. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

We are particularly interested in the temporal stability analysis on a 1D computational domain ($k_z = 0$). The fluids are confined in the vertical direction, and consequently homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions are used on the top and bottom boundaries $y = \pm H$.

In the classical 1D instability analysis of the VRTI, a periodic solution with unlimited wavelength in both the horizontal x and spanwise z directions [20] is assumed.

Substitution of the ansatz (15) into the perturbation equations (12)-(14) yields

$$ik_x \hat{p} - \mu(D^2 - k^2)\hat{u} - D\mu(ik_x \hat{v} + D\hat{u}) - 2\bar{\rho}\hat{v}\Omega_z = -\gamma\bar{\rho}\hat{u} \quad (18)$$

$$D\hat{p} - \mu(D^2 - k^2)\hat{v} - 2D\mu D\hat{v} + \hat{\rho} + 2k^2 S\hat{\xi}\delta_s(y - y_s) + 2\bar{\rho}\hat{u}\Omega_z = -\gamma\bar{\rho}\hat{v} \quad (19)$$

$$ik_z \hat{p} - \mu(D^2 - k^2)\hat{w} - D\mu(ik_z \hat{v} + D\hat{w}) = -\gamma\bar{\rho}\hat{w} \quad (20)$$

$$D\bar{\rho}\hat{v} = -\gamma\hat{\rho} \quad (21)$$

$$ik_x \hat{u} + ik_z \hat{w} = -D\hat{v} \quad (22)$$

where $k^2 = k_x^2 + k_z^2$ and $D = d/dy$. Here we make use of the regularized Dirac delta function

$$\delta(y - y_s) = \frac{D\bar{\rho}}{2A_\rho} \quad (23)$$

The set of equations (18)-(22) with the equation

$$\hat{v} = \frac{\partial \hat{\xi}}{\partial t} = \gamma\hat{\xi} \quad (24)$$

form a system of six differential equations.

In order to simplify the system from six to five differential equations, we eliminate the displacement $\hat{\xi}$ from the aforementioned system. To do this, we combine (21) and (24), so

$$\hat{\xi} = -\frac{\hat{\rho}}{D\bar{\rho}} \quad (25)$$

Inserting equation (25) into equation (19) and making use of the regularized Dirac delta function (23), we obtain

$$D\hat{p} - \mu(D^2 - k^2)\hat{v} - 2D\mu D\hat{v} + \hat{\rho}(1 - k^2 S/A_\rho) + 2\bar{\rho}\hat{u}\Omega_z = -\gamma\bar{\rho}\hat{v} \quad (26)$$

Multiplying equations (18) and (20) by ik_x and ik_z , respectively and making use of equation (22) we obtain

$$k^2 \hat{p} = [-\gamma\bar{\rho} + \mu(D^2 - k^2)] D\hat{v} + (D\mu)(D^2 + k^2 - 2ik_x \bar{\rho}\Omega_z)\hat{v} \quad (27)$$

Using equations (21), (26) and (27), we obtain a generalized eigenvalue problem reduced to a third order system where the eigenfunctions are the amplitudes of the disturbances of the vertical velocity \hat{v} , density $\hat{\rho}$, pressure \hat{p} .

For simplicity, we set $k_z = 0$ and $\hat{w} = 0$. Thus, $k = k_x$ and $\omega_y = 0$. Now eliminating \hat{u} between equations (22) and (26) we obtain

$$D\hat{p} - \mu (D^2 - k^2) \hat{v} - 2D\mu D\hat{v} + \hat{\rho}(1 - k^2 S/A_\rho) + 2i\bar{\rho}\Omega_z D\hat{v}/k = -\gamma\bar{\rho}\hat{v} \quad (28)$$

Thus, equations (21), (27), (28) form a system of three differential equations for vertical velocity \hat{v} , perturbed pressure \hat{p} and perturbed density $\hat{\rho}$. Here the generalized eigenvalue problem for the determination of γ may thus be written as

$$A \begin{pmatrix} \hat{v} \\ \hat{p} \\ \hat{\rho} \end{pmatrix} = \gamma B \begin{pmatrix} \hat{v} \\ \hat{p} \\ \hat{\rho} \end{pmatrix} \quad (29)$$

where the matrix A and B can be expressed, respectively, as

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} -k\mu (D^2 - k^2) - 2kD\mu D + 2i\bar{\rho}\Omega_z D & kD & k(1 - k^2 S/A_\rho) \\ \mu (D^3 - k^2 D) + D\mu (D^2 + k^2) - 2ik\bar{\rho}\Omega_z & -k^2 & 0 \\ D\bar{\rho} & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (30)$$

and

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} -k\bar{\rho} & 0 & 0 \\ \bar{\rho}D & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -I \end{pmatrix} \quad (31)$$

The boundary conditions are

$$\hat{v}(\pm H) = 0, D\hat{v}(\pm H) = 0 \quad (32)$$

IV. RESULTS

For a given wave number k, the eigenvalue problem given by expressions and (29)-(32) are numerically solved using the respective boundary conditions, which gives the eigenvalues and the corresponding eigenfunctions. A spectral Chebyshev collocation and a finite element scheme are used for the 1D domain.

1. *Non viscous case*

It is straightforward to show that for the *inviscid* (*i.e.*, $\mu = D\mu = 0$) the system (29) can be reduced to only one dimensionless stability equation for the vertical velocity perturbation \hat{v}

$$A\gamma^2 + B\gamma + C = 0 \quad (33)$$

where A , B and C are, respectively,

$$A = k^2\bar{\rho}\hat{v} - D\bar{\rho}D\hat{v} - \bar{\rho}D^2\hat{v} \quad (34)$$

$$B = -2ik\Omega_z D\bar{\rho}\hat{v} \quad (35)$$

$$C = -k^2D\bar{\rho}(1 - k^2S/A_\rho)\hat{v} \quad (36)$$

We now specialize to the case of a density function involving unit step function $\Theta(y)$, *i.e.*, the case of two finite-thickness fluids of constant density

$$\bar{\rho} = 1 - A_\rho + 2A_\rho\Theta(y) \quad (37)$$

Thus, 33 reduces to

$$(D^2 - k^2)\hat{v} = 0 \quad (38)$$

The general solution of 38 can be written in the form

$$\hat{v} = C_1e^{-ky} + C_2e^{ky}, \quad -H \leq z < 0, \quad (39a)$$

$$\hat{v} = C_3e^{-ky} + C_4e^{ky}, \quad 0 < z \leq H. \quad (39b)$$

Following Chandrasekhar [19], a jump condition can be obtained by integrating 33 across the boundary $y = y_s$, between $y_s - \epsilon$ and $y_s + \epsilon$ and then assuming $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$. In view of the continuity of \hat{v} across $y = y_s$ and the boundness of $\bar{\rho}$ this limiting process gives

$$\gamma^2\Delta_s(\bar{\rho}D\hat{v}) + 2ik\gamma\Omega_z\Delta_s\bar{\rho}\hat{v}_s + k^2\left(1 - \frac{k^2S}{A_\rho}\right)\Delta_s\bar{\rho}\hat{v}_s = 0 \quad (40)$$

where $\Delta_s(f) = f(y_s + 0) - f(y_s - 0)$ is the jump, which a quantity f experiences at the interface $y = y_s$. The subscript s distinguishes the value of a quantity known to be continuous at an interface, which takes at $y = y_s$.

$$C_1 e^{kH} + C_2 e^{-kH} = 0 \quad (41)$$

$$C_3 e^{-kH} + C_4 e^{kH} = 0 \quad (42)$$

$$C_1 + C_2 = C_3 + C_4 \quad (43)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \gamma^2 [(1 + A_\rho)(-C_3 k + k C_4) - (1 - A_\rho)(-C_1 k + k C_2)] \\ & + 2ik\gamma\Omega_z [(1 + A_\rho)(C_3 + C_4) - (1 - A_\rho)(C_1 + C_2)] \\ & + k^2 (1 - k^2 S/A_\rho) [(1 + A_\rho)(C_3 + C_4) - (1 - A_\rho)(C_1 + C_2)] = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

The following equations determine the four constant C_1 , C_2 , C_3 y C_4 . Equations (41) and (42) express $D\hat{v} = 0$ at $y = -H$ and $y = H$, respectively. Equation (43) follows from the continuity of \hat{v} at $y = 0$. Finally, equation (44) is the jump condition (40) written in detail. Equations 41-44 can be written in the form $MV = 0$, where M is an 4×4 matrix and V is a vector having the four constant C_1 through C_4 as its elements. A nontrivial solution is obtained only if $\text{Det}(M) = 0$ and this equation determines an analytical expression for the eigenvalue $\gamma = \sigma + i\omega$, being the growth rate

$$\sigma = \sqrt{kA_\rho \tan(kH) - \Omega^2 A_\rho^2 \tan(kH)^2 - Sk^3 \tan(kH)} \quad (45)$$

and the frequency

$$\omega = \Omega_z A_\rho \tan(kH) \quad (46)$$

In this case and according to [16], different from the traditional RTI, the unstable modes are not stationary but traveling waves. Mathematically speaking, the eigenvalue γ becomes a complex number when the system is unstable in contrast to the real value obtained when vertical rotation is imposed alone.

As a previous validation the inviscid limit is studied. Results are compared in Fig. 1 y 2 and all modes agree very well with the values γ obtained from corrected expressions 45 and 46 for finite domains of length $2H$.

FIG. 1: Growth rate instability as a function of the wave number, for $A_\rho = 0.2$, $L_s = 0.01$, $H = 6$, $\Omega_z = 0.8$ and $S = 0.2$.

FIG. 2: Frequency instability as a function of the wave number, for $A_\rho = 0.2$, $L_s = 0.01$, $H = 6$, $\Omega_z = 0.8$ and $S = 0.2$.

First, the inviscid case is analyzed. Looking for the cut-off wave number, i.e. the wave number where the growth rate vanishes. Fig. 3 shows the dependence of the dimensionless cut-off k_c wave number as a function of the dimensionless angular velocity Ω_z for different dimensionless thicknesses H of the fluids, being the dimensionless surface tension and the Atwood number $S = 0.2$ and $A_\rho = 0.2$, respectively.

In general it is observed, for a given angular velocity, the existence of two cut-off wave numbers. The upper cutoff wave number k_c^+ is the result of the joint action of surface tension and the Coriolis force. This last force reinforces the action of the first one, since that cut-off wave number decreases with respect to the case in which there is no rotation $k_c = 1$. On the other hand, the lower cut-off wave number k_c^- is due to the exclusive action of the Coriolis force.

For the case of $H \rightarrow \infty$ and $\Omega_z = 1.135$, the upper wave is $k_c^+ = 0.828394$ and $k_c^- = 0.140303$. Therefore, it can be deduced that the cut-off wave number, due to the exclusive action of surface tension in the absence of rotation ($k_c = 1$), has decreased by about 17% due to the action of rotation. In order to analyze the effect of finite thickness, we consider the particular case of $H = 3$ and $\Omega_z = 1.135$. We can verify that the upper cut-off wave number is $k_c^+ = 0.833726$, i.e. it increases with respect to that corresponding to the case $H \rightarrow \infty$. Furthermore, it is observed that for a given thickness H there is a critical angular velocity Ω_z^* above which the modes are stable. For the case $H = 3$, we obtain $\Omega_z^* = 1.43957$. Likewise, as H decreases, Ω_z^* increases.

FIG. 3: Cut-off wave number k_c as a function of angular velocity Ω_z , for $A_\rho = 0.2$ and $S = 0.2$ for different values of fluid dimensionless thickness H .

2. Viscous case

First, a validation of the Matlab code in 1D geometry is carried out for $L_s = 0.01$, $\Omega_z = 0$, $H = 1$. As shown in fig. 4, the instability growth rates for the cases $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.2$,

$S = 0.003$ and $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.6$, $S = 0.01$ show a good agreement with those obtained in the 2D geometry [10].

FIG. 4: Growth rate of the instability as a function of the wave number for $L_s = 0.01$ and $H = 1$. Validations are performed by using those obtained in 2D geometry for the cases $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.2$, $S = 0.003$ and $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.6$, $S = 0.01$

Secondly, the viscous case is considered. In Fig. 5 the growth rate has been represented for $L_s = 0.01$, $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.2$, $H = 1$ and $S = 0.003$ as a function of the wave number k for three different cases: the first with $\Omega_z = 0$, the second with $\Omega_z = 20$ and the third $\Omega_z = 40$. An examination of this figure shows three features: for a given k , σ decreases with increasing Ω_z (except for long wave numbers), that σ_{max} decreases with increasing Ω_z , k_{max} increases with increasing Ω_z and σ vanishes for a critical wave number $k_c = 8.2$. Here, that the cut-off wave number of the surface tension remains unchanged with respect to the case of absence of rotation. However, the growth rate of instability is reduced, as found in

previous works [12], [15].

FIG. 5: Growth rate of the instability as a function of the wave number, for $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.2$, $L_s = 0.01$, $H = 1$, $S = 0.003$ for $\Omega_z = 0$, $\Omega_z = 20$ and $\Omega_z = 40$.

On the other hand, it is found that the dimensionless wavelength of the maximum instability mode λ_m decreases with an increase in angular velocity Ω_z until it reaches an asymptotic value that is not reached when the effect of surface tension is neglected. The graph shows that for the case $H = 1$, $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.2$, $S = 0.0003$ this asymptotic value is $\lambda_m \approx 0.997331$.

FIG. 6: Plot of the wavelenght λ_m of the fastest growing mode against angular velocity Ω_z

V. CONCLUSIONS

The most important conclusions obtained in this work are the following:

- Neglecting viscosity, the cut-off wave numbers due to rotation and surface tension depend on the thickness of the fluids and the angular velocity. Therefore, this shows that the cut-off wavenumber due to surface tension is not always independent of the thickness of the fluids as previously believed. Furthermore, when the thickness of the fluids decreases, the number of excited RTI modes increases. Actually, this is because a decrease in such a thickness leads to an increase in the angular velocity above which the system is stable.

- For the viscous case, the cut-off wave number due to surface tension is independent of the rotation, as well as the thickness of the fluids. Also, it is found that, due to surface tension, the wavelength of the mode of maximum instability saturates for very large angular velocities.
- We have found that, the viscosity leads to the disappearance of the cut-off wavenumber (due only to rotation) below which there is no instability.

Acknowledgements

- [1] Lord Rayleigh, “Investigation of the character of the equilibrium of an incompressible heavy fluid of variable density,” Proc. London Math Soc **s1-14**, 170–177 (1883).
- [2] G. I. Taylor, “Instability of liquid surfaces when accelerated in a direction perpendicular to their planes,” Proc. R. Soc. London **192**, 201 (1950).
- [3] R. E. Rosensweig, Y. Hirota, S. Tsuda, and K. Raj, “Study of audio speakers containing ferrofluid,” J. Phys.: Condens. Matter **20**, 204147 (2008).
- [4] C. Harig, P. Molnar, and G. A. Houseman, “Rayleigh-Taylor instability under a shear stress free top boundary condition and its relevance to removal of mantle lithosphere from beneath the sierra nevada,” Tectonics **27**, TC6019 (2008).
- [5] T. M. Willey, K. Champley, R. Hodgkin, L. Lauderbach, M. Bagge-Hansen, C. May, N. Sanchez, B. J. Jensen, A. Iverson, and T. van Buuren, “X-ray imaging and 3D reconstruction of in-flight exploding foil initiation flyers,” J. Appl. Phys. **119**, 235901 (2016).
- [6] T. G. Theofanous, “Aerobreakup of newtonian and viscoelastic liquids,” Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech. **43**, 661 (2011).
- [7] A. A. Blinova, M. M. Romanova, and R. V. E. Lovelace, “Boundary between stable and unstable regimes of accretion. ordered and chaotic unstable regimes,” Mon. Not. R. Astron. Soc. **459**, 2354 (2016).
- [8] A. Tavakoli, L. Hadzievski, and D. D. Tskhakayab, “Rayleigh-Taylor instability of magnetized density transition layer,” Phys. Plasmas **7**, 89–93 (1999).
- [9] K. O. Mikaelian, “Rayleigh-Taylor instability in finite-thickness fluids with viscosity and surface tension,” Phys. Rev. E **54**, 3676 (1996).

- [10] J. Martínez-Carrascal, Calderón-Sánchez, L. M. González-Gutiérrez, and A. de Andrea González, “Extended computation of the viscous rayleigh-taylor instability in a horizontally confined flow,” *Phys. Rev. E* **103**, 053114 (2021).
- [11] R. Hide, “The character of the equilibrium of a heavy, viscous, incompressible, rotating fluid of variable density: I.general theory,” *Q. J. Mech. Appl. Math.* **9**, 22–34 (1956).
- [12] R. Hide, “The character of the equilibrium of a heavy, viscous, incompressible, rotating fluid of variable density: Ii. two special cases,” *Q. J. Mech. Appl. Math.* **9**, 35–50 (1956).
- [13] S. Chandrasekhar, *Hydrodynamic and hydromagnetic stability* (Courier Dover Publications, 2013).
- [14] P.K. Sharmaa, R.P. Prajapatib, and R.K. Chhajlanib, “Effect of surface tension and rotation on rayleigh-taylor instability of two superposed fluids with suspended particles,” *Acta Phys. Pol. A* **118**, 576–584 (2010).
- [15] K. A. Baldwin, M. M. Scase, and Richard J. A. Hill, “The Inhibition of the Rayleigh-Taylor Instability by rotation,” **5**, 11706 (2015).
- [16] J. J. Tao, X. T. He, W. H. Ye, and F. H. Busse, “Nonlinear Rayleigh-Taylor instability of rotating inviscid fluids,” *Phys. Rev. E* **87**, 013001 (2013).
- [17] L. M. González-Gutiérrez and A. de Andrea González, “Numerical computation of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability for a viscous fluid with regularized interface properties,” *Phys. Review E* **100**, 013101 (2019).
- [18] R. Hide, “The character of the equilibrium of a heavy, viscous, incompressible, rotating fluids of variable density. i. general theory,” *Quart. J. Mech. Appl. Math.* **9**, 22–34 (1955).
- [19] S. Chandrasekhar, *Hydrodynamic and Hydromagnetic Stability* (Dover, New-York, 1981).
- [20] C. X. Yu, C. Xue, J. Liu, X. Y. Hu, Y. Y. Liu, W. H. Ye, L. F. Wang, J. F. Wu, and Z. F. Fan, “Multiple eigenmodes of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability observed for a fluid interface with smoothly varying density,” *Phys. Rev. E* **97**, 013102 (2018).